

COMPARISON OF SIMULATION MODEL AND PLANT DATA OF A CRUSHING - GRINDING CIRCUIT

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ABSTRACT. Increasing complexity of ore deposits requires operations to be continuously improving their cost competitiveness. Mathematical modelling and process simulation techniques are useful tools to understand the process, define bottlenecks and increase process efficiencies. This paper presents a crushing and grinding circuit of a chromite ore gravity separation plant simulation model results and actual plant operating data. Throughout the study, jaw crusher, ball and rod mill summary equipment characteristics, breakage and selection functions employed, comparison of particle size distribution curves of site process streams to model results are presented. Simulation work is completed by using METSIM® software. The paper also showcases ease of flow diagram and process data presentation by the utilisation of the adequate simulation approach.

Key words: crushing-grinding circuit, chromite ore, process simulation, breakage, selection function

Introduction

Modelling and simulation application to process plants has an important role in operational and business case development. Relying solely on engineering estimates or vendor information lacks interdependent technical data of the plant streams, and dynamic interaction of each stream with one another.

Process simulation also allows experimenting various process options within fewer time frames and with more precise results compared to the spreadsheet approach. It provides having the process flowsheet, mass or energy balances, particle size distributions, plant discharge mediums in any phases, or energy consumptions under one roof. Employing simulation software enables the users to change any process parameter quickly without having to edit upstream or downstream formula connections. Additionally, using adequate software and simulation approach provides getting outputs from one resource that would easily provide input for other project departments such as finance by providing OPEX or CAPEX data, or discharge tonnage with contaminants for environmental department.

Presented simulation of the crushing and grinding circuit demonstrated the ability to consider many variables simultaneously. Throughout the paper, process streams sampling results for particle size distribution were compared to the simulation results and main equipment characteristics used as input for the simulation model were shown.

Materials and methods

Processed ore that is subject to this study is a chromite ore with average feed grade of 12%. Ore body is associated with serpentine and olivine minerals. Chromite particles are in round shapes with sizes between 50 µm and 1600 µm with average size of 450 µm.

SEM picture of the chromite particles is shown on Figure 1.

Plant crushing (partial) and grinding circuit are presented on Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Jaw crushers are generally employed as first stage crushing for the size reduction of large size ore.

Fig. 1. Chromite particles associated with serpentine and olivine (Ozan, 2007)

Fig. 2. Plant grinding circuit

Fig. 3. Plant crushing circuit (Partial)

This type of crusher primarily operates as compression crusher (Gupta and Yan, 2006). Parameters of the jaw crusher utilised at the plant operations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Jaw crusher parameters

Close side setting (CS), mm	120
Open side setting (OS), mm	247
Throw (TH), mm	127
Motor (kW)	110

Rod mills are generally placed between crushing equipment and ball mill (Duroudier, 2016). Yield of the rod mill at the plant is lower compared to ball mill, whereas the motor capacity is double as the energy consumption of the rod mill is higher compared to the ball mill. Table 2 shows the plant rod mill parameters.

Table 2. Rod mill parameters

Size, mm	D 2440 x L 2660
RPM	21
Motor size (kW)	250
Rod addition	26 Mton
RPM	19
Discharge slurry % solids	60

As with the rod mill, ball mills reduce size of fed ore particles by impact and attrition during dropping of the steel media near the top of the rotating cylindrical shell (Neikov et al, 2019). Parameters of the ball mill are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Ball mill parameters

Size, mm	D 2130 x L 2330
RPM	14
Motor size (kW)	125
Ball addition	11 Mton
RPM	21
Discharge slurry % solids	65

All software model inputs were established by using the actual plant equipment characteristics. For the scope of this paper, only the jaw crusher and grinding mills parameters are presented.

Modelling work

During the process simulation work mathematical equations are employed to model the plant processing streams. Modelling the complex particle size distribution (PSD) of plant circuits provides advantage on making accurate decisions and facilitates understanding of the process (Barlett, 1987).

Each equipment of the plant was presented on the METSIM flowsheet. Crushing and grinding circuit flowsheets prepared on METSIM are shown on Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Jaw crusher modelling was completed by using the METSIM jaw crushing empirical calculation option.

Software empirical calculation uses the US Bureau of Mines (USBM) method to estimate crusher product size distribution.

Fig. 4. Crushing circuit flowsheet

Fig. 5. Grinding circuit flowsheet

Screen size analysis of crushed material uses the following equation:

$$SS = A + (B) (Z) + (C) (Z^2) + (D) (Z^3) \quad (1)$$

Constants in the formula are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Screen size analysis formula constants

A	B	C	D
71.3174	20.9630	2.34755	0.091640

$$Z = -0.7 + \text{Lnsr2 CS} - \text{Lnsr2 MIC} \quad (2)$$

where CS, MIC and Lnsr2 are crusher closed side setting, METSIM variable screen size fraction micron sizes and Logarithm to the base of the square root of two, respectively.

Software selection function formulation for crushed material is as follows,

$$\text{SF} = 2 * (\text{Lnsr2 MIC} - \text{Lnsr2 CS}) \quad (3)$$

Crusher discharge material screen size analysis is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{SSAd} = (\text{SS})(\text{SF}) + (\text{SSAf})(1 - \text{SF}) \quad (4)$$

where SSAf is screen size analysis of the feed material to the crusher.

Based on the laboratory test work ball mill and rod mill work index (W_i) were 17.08 and 16.23, respectively.

During ball mill model calculations, the *bond inside length* calculation option was employed. In this option, mill inside length is used as input and the software model calculates P_{80} .

Bond's breakage and selection equations used throughout the modelling are as follows:

$$B(X, Y) = \frac{1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{X}{Y}\right) * BE\right]}{1 - \exp[-1]} \quad (5)$$

$$S(X) = \frac{AA[1] * \left(\frac{X}{1000}\right) * AA[2]}{1 + \left(\frac{X}{AA[3]}\right) * AA[4]} \quad (6)$$

Coefficients utilised for the equations were as follows:

BE = 1.0; AA[1] = 1.1; AA[3] = 1600

AA[2] = 0.9; AA[4] = 3.0

For the rod mill modelling, calculation option employed was *simulate* where mill dimensions are used and P_{80} was calculated.

Selection function coefficient AL and breakage function BE utilised are, 0.5 and 1, respectively.

Rod mill selection and breakage function are as follows:

$$B(X, Y) = \frac{1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{X}{Y}\right) * BE\right]}{1 - \exp[-1]} \quad (7)$$

$$S(X) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{X}{1000}\right) * AL\right] \quad (8)$$

Results and discussion

The results of each stream are presented on the output particle size distribution diagrams of the software. For the scope of this paper, jaw crusher, ball and rod mill results are compared with site data. Figure 6 and Figure 7 present the particle size distribution plant streams.

Primary crusher feed site data and simulation results are presented on Figure 8.

Oversize material from single deck screen with 2 meter wide and 6 meter long with aperture size of 125 mm was fed to the jaw crusher, stream 4 on Figure 4. The feed PSD site data closely matches the simulation results.

Fig. 6. Crushing circuit PSD output

Fig. 7. Grinding circuit PSD output

Primary crusher product site data and simulation results are presented on Figure 9. Both simulation and site data had similar particle size distributions.

For the ball and rod mill products, the simulation method selected aimed to calculate P_{80} .

The results of the P_{80} points for both ball and rod mill simulation discharge streams were closely matched with the site data. Data for ball mill feed are presented in Figure 10.

During building of the model, the dimensions of the mills were readily available and one of the aims of this simulation study was defining P_{80} point for the mill discharge.

For that reason, *bond inside length* calculation option for ball mill and *simulate* options for rod mill calculations were selected which required mill equipment parameters, and clearly the mill feed PSD data. By using these two input groups and calculation methods, simulation model gave the P_{80} of the mills' discharge streams.

For a more detailed mill discharge PSD curve that would closely match the sampled site data rod mill *parameterise* option is recommended to be selected by entering breakage and selectivity function coefficients to the software.

On the ball mill simulation side, selection and breakage functions coefficients could have been improved in order to calculate a complete PSD curve, if the PSD data of the plant streams was readily available at the time of the simulation model was built.

As a summary, the software was only assigned to calculate the P_{80} of the mill discharge since the model built was completed at pre-operation period. The resulting P_{80} values obtained from the model were close to the actual site data.

Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 13 present the ball mill

Fig. 8. Jaw crusher feed PSD site data vs. simulation results

Fig. 11. Ball mill product site data vs. simulation

Fig. 9. Jaw crusher product site data vs. simulation

Fig. 12. Rod mill feed site data vs. simulation

Fig. 10. Ball mill feed site data vs. simulation

Fig. 13. Rod mill product site data vs. simulation

product, rod mill feed and rod mill product PSD comparison between the model and the site data.

Conclusion

This paper presented and compared results of the process simulation model and actual site data of a gravity separation plant crushing and grinding circuit. Sampling campaign results for particle size analysis are presented along mathematical model results.

At this current model, complex interaction of the comminution and size separation of a complete gravity separation plant was modelled by utilising METSIM software. For the purpose of the paper, only jaw crusher and comminution streams data were published in detail. Each modelled stream discussed throughout this study showed close relation to the actual plant data, paper showcased the advantages of using a modelling software and also calculation method selection effect on the final model output.

Compliance of ethical standards

Author declares that there is no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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